

Does Household Consumption Expenditure Improves During Covid-19 in Nigeria: an Overview of Pre and Post Era

Author's Details:

Ifeoma C. Nwakoby¹ Charles O. Manasseh (Corresponding)² Kenechukwu K. Ede³

^{1&2}Department of Banking & Finance, University of Nigeria, Enugu Campus

³Department of Economics, University of Nigeria, Nsukka

Abstract:

This study reviews the effect of covid-19 on household consumption expenditure during pre and post covid-19 era. In order to examine if household consumption expenditure improved or not, we examined measures such as household consumption expenditure, purchasing power parity (PPP), foreign remittances, household disposable income, and household consumer confidence was assessed from 2015 to 2021 and the findings shows that covid-19 contributed to fall in Nigerian household consumption expenditure. We captured the growth in consumption in real and nominal terms, consumptions made by households, government, individual and non-profit institutions serving households (NPISH) was assessed and it was discovered that growth on consumption occurred in the aforesaid economic agents. Again, the well-being of the households examined using poverty headcounts, level of happiness, hunger index, and prosperity index and it was discovered that due to outbreak of covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria, the rate of poverty headcounts increased during and post covid-19 era was high; the level of happiness diminished and rate of hunger increased. Policies such are government improvement of agricultural sector and economic diversification was suggested since the study concludes that covid-19 pandemic have great negative impact in household consumption expenditure.

Keywords: Household Consumption, Expenditure, covid-19

1 introduction

Household consumption remains the basic activity in an economy. It is the seen as transaction of the national account of income account representing consumer spending. It consist of the expenditure incurred by resident households on individual consumption on goods and services. Consumption expenditure is an important factor in determining economic growth for any country. The outbreak of covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria crumbled the general economic activities. Nigerians suffered the effect of covid-19 lockdown in the second quarter of the year 2020 and consumption expenditure dropped. Covid-19 affected the global travel business, national healthcare systems, the food industry, education sector and service sector. Due to globalization, there are expectations of spillover effects to emerging and developing countries due to their dependence on developed countries for importation of good and services (Ozili and Arun, 2020). Nigerians spent a total of N46.99 trillion on household consumption expenditure in the first half of 2020 (January – June) in nominal terms, indicating a 4.2% decline compared to N49.06 trillion recorded in the corresponding period of 2019. Household consumption expenditure was 8.62% in Q1 of 2020 at N25.49 trillion, while it collapsed by 15.96% at N21.5 trillion in the second quarter of the year (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). Nigerian economy contracted by 6.1% in the second quarter of 2020, and consequently slipped into recession after enduring a second contraction in Q3 2020. This decline can be attributed to the disruptions brought about by the lockdown as a result of covid-19 pandemic (Nairametrics, 2020).

The outbreak of covid-19 pandemic majorly hit Nigerian economy greatly; it affected the borrowers' capacity to service their loans, which gave rise to non-performing loans (NPLs) that depressed banks' earnings and eventually impaired banks' soundness and stability, it created oil demand shocks which was reflected in the sharp decline in oil price from US\$60 per barrel to as low as US\$30 per barrel in March, it created shocks in the global supply chain as many importers shut down their factories and closed their borders particularly China and Nigerian economy was severely affected because it is an import-dependent country and as a result Nigeria witnessed shortage of crucial supplies like pharmaceutical supplies, spare parts and finished goods from China, national budget was greatly affected, the budget was initially planned with an oil price of US\$57 per barrel, fell

to US\$30 per barrel during the pandemic, which makes the budget to be obsolete, finally, covid-19 pandemic affected the Nigerian stock market, it made investors loose over NGN2,3 trillion (US\$5.9bn) barely three weeks of announcement of first case of covid-19 case in Nigeria (Ozili, P.K., 2020).

Many extensive studies have been conducted to examine the effect of Covid-19 household consumption and economic activities (see: Atkeson, 2020; Fernandes, 2020; Mckibbin and Fernando, 2020; Altig et al, 2020; Ozili and Arun 2020) among others. There is dearth of existing literature specifically to examine how Covid-19 pandemic affect household consumption and economic activities in Nigeria. Thus, this study fills the gap in the literature by examining effects of covid-19 on household consumption expenditure in Nigeria. Measures such as household consumption expenditure, personal income, household per capita income, remittances in Nigeria, level of happiness, poverty headcount, prosperity index, and hunger index will be evaluated by comparing their outcomes in the pre and post covid-19 era. Thus, the subsequent sections will be structured as follows. Section 2; evaluation of household consumption expenditure in Nigeria in pre and post covid-19 era. Section 3; evaluation of economic welfare in pre and post covid-19 era in Nigeria. Section 4; government efforts towards welfare maximization of Nigerians in pre and post covid-19 era. Section 5; summary, policy implications and conclusion.

2. Evaluation of Household Consumption Expenditure in Nigeria in Pre and Post Covid-19 Era

The outbreak of covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria disrupted economic activities of Nigerians and affected agri-food system production. The government's policy measures such as travel restrictions, lockdowns, and restrictions on economic and social activities, aimed at curbing the spread of Covid-19, affected the livelihoods and food security of smallholders in Nigeria. Before the pandemic, Nigerian government had been grappling with weak recovery from the 2014 oil price shock, with GDP growth revolving around 2.3 percent in 2019. In February 2020, the IMF stated that GDP growth rate fell from 2.5 percent to 2 percent, as a result of relatively low oil prices and limited fiscal space. The country's debt profile has been a source of concern for policymakers and development practitioners with estimate of 60 percent, which is likely to worsen amid the steep decline in revenue associated with falling oil prices. These constraining factors made the impact of covid-19 outbreak to worsen the economic situation of Nigeria.

Table one below shows the effects of covid-19 pandemic on components of household consumption in pre and post covid-19 era in Nigeria. Household consumption expenditure was as US\$390billion in 2015, and reduced to US\$329billion in 2016. In 2017, household consumption expenditure was US\$301billion but went as low as US\$22.7billion in 2018. However, in 2019, household consumption expenditure was US\$49.0billion. Following the outbreak of covid-19 pandemic, household consumption expenditure reduced to US\$46billion and collapsed further to US\$39.2billion in post covid-19 era. Furthermore, Nigerian purchasing power parity (PPP) was US\$5514.8 in 2015, and US\$4935.2 in 2016. It collapsed to US\$839.4 in 2017, and even further to US\$257.34 in 2018. It appreciated to US\$6847 in 2019. In covid-19 era, the value of PPP was US\$103. Thus, in the period of post covid-19 era Nigerian PPP appreciated to US\$902. Remittance is also considered as component of household consumption expenditure. It measure the total amount of money remitted to Nigeria by diaspora Nigerian either for investment or household consumption. As at 2015, Nigerian remittances stood at US\$1035million, it slacked down to US\$744million in 2016, even lower to US\$275million, and US\$68million in 2017 and 2018 respectively and it later appreciated a little to US\$90million in 2019. In the year 2020 foreign remittance to Nigeria by diaspora Nigerians greatly collapsed to US\$15million which was due to outbreak of covid-19. Government policies such as ban on business travels and other strict measures towards curbing covid-19 is seen as major reason behind low international remittances to Nigeria and in the year 2021 – post covid-19 epoch, Nigerian foreign remittances grew to US\$22million.

In addition, household disposable income affects the expenditure of households in an economy. It seen as a measure of the combined incomes of all people sharing a particular household or place of residence. It includes every form of income such as salaries and wages, retirement income, near cash government transfers like food

stamps and investment gains (Wikipedia). The value of household disposable income in Nigeria in 2015 is N170million, it went up to N195million in 2016 and even as high as N201million in 2017. It wings down to N196million in 2018 and grew up to N200million in 2019. It the wake of the outbreak of covid-19, household disposable income collapsed to N172million and grew up to N234million in post covid-19 era. This study examines another influencer of household consumption – consumer confidence. Consumer confidence is an economic indicator that measures the degree of optimism that consumers have regarding the overall state of the country’s economy and their own financial situations. Evidence from the findings made by this study shows that in pre covid-19 era household consumer confidence of Nigerians was -4.4% in 2015, it grew to -2.01% in 2016 and moved even more than the previous years at -47.92% in 2017. However in 2018, it appreciated to 2.05% and 10.34% in 2019. Following the outbreak of coronavirus in the year 2020, household consumer confidence collapsed to 4.78% and even decreased further to -15.04% in 2021 in post covid-19 era.

Table1: Household Consumption in Pre and Post Covid-19 Era

	PRE COVID-19 ERA					COVID-19 ERA	POST COVID-19 ERA
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
HOUSEHOLD CONSUMPTION EXPENDITURE	N390billion	N329billio n	N301billi on	N22.7billi on	N49.06bill ion	N46billion	N39.2billion
PURCHASING POWER PARITY	US\$5514.8	US\$4935. 2	US\$839.4	US\$257.3 4	US\$6847	US\$103	US902
FOREIGN REMITTANCES	US\$1035mil lion	US\$744mi llion	US\$275m illion	US\$68mill ion	US\$90mill ion	US\$15millio n	US\$22million
HOUSEHOLD DISPOSABLE INCOME	N170million	N195milli on	N201milli on	N196milli on	N200milli on	N172million	N234million
HOUSEHOLD CONSUMER CONFIDENCE	-4.4%	-2.01%	-47.92%	2.05%	10.34%	4.78%	-15.04%

Source: Central Bank of Nigeria and National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria.

Household final consumption of Nigeria in the real terms, grew by 6.10% and 16.59% in Q3 and Q4 2020, respectively on a year on year basis, compared to the -1.98% growth in Q3 2019 and -0.41% growth in Q4 2019. Real household consumption expenditure rose by 0.81% from -1.06% recorded in 2019. On a quarter to quarter basis, real household consumption expenditure grew by 38.85% in Q3 and 20.76% in Q4 2020. In the nominal terms, household final consumption expenditure grew by -1.83% in Q3, and -0.71% in Q4 2020, resulting to annual growth rate of -1.48%. The annual growth rate was -11.33% points slower than recorded in the previous year. On a quarter basis, economic growth rate recorded was 23.04% in Q3 and 7.68% in Q4 2020, when compared to the preceding year’s 11.74% and 6.46% in the corresponding quarters. Household consumption accounted for 63.63% of the real GDP at market prices in Q3 2020, and even higher at 70.45% in Q4 2020.

Table 2: Growth in Consumption Components in Covid-19 Era in Real Terms

Growth in Consumption Components, 2019 and 2020 (Real – Percentage)								
Year	2019				2020			
Quarter	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Year on Year (YoY)								
Households	-2.68	0.75	-1.98	-0.41	-4.86	-18.11	6.10	16.59
NPISH	-3.25	7.84	53.77	7.92	-0.38	174.87	289.76	41854
Government	8.88	0.14	2.26	22.38	6.80	148.29	99.18	12.13
Individual	-41.59	-28.86	-33.32	-19.61	-1.81	158.30	106.49	15.75
Collective	52.31	15.70	24.09	47.85	9.65	114.99	96.78	10.93
Quarter on Quarter (QoQ)								
Quarter	2019				2020			
Quarter	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Households	-20.47	6.33	7.18	9.89	-24.03	-8.48	38.85	20.76
NPISH	23.68	-56.40	45.71	37.37	14.17	20.29	106.61	82.75
Government	-4.04	-5.84	2.19	32.54	-16.26	118.90	-18.02	-25.39
Individual	-36.96	-5.85	2.15	32.58	-22.99	147.68	-18.34	-25.68
Collective	15.92	-5.84	2.20	32.53	-14.03	110.40	-17.91	-25.29

Source: World Bank Data Base

Final consumption expenditure by non-profit institutions serving households (NPISH) recorded growth rate of 289.76% in Q3 and 418.54% in Q4 2020, year on year in real terms. For annual 2020, growth in the real expenditure for this component was recorded at 212.36% year on year. Quarter on quarter, growth in the real NPISH expenditure stood at 106.61% in Q3 but dropped to 82.75% in Q4 2020. This expenditure component accounted for 1.30% of real GDP expenditure at market price in Q3 and a share of 2.19% in Q4 2020. For it accounts for 1.24% of total real GDP expenditure at market prices.

Table 3 Growth in Consumption Components in Covid-19 Era in Nominal Term

Growth in Consumption Components, 2019 and 2020 (Nominal – Percentage)								
Year	2019				2020			
Quarter	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Year on Year (YoY)								
Households	7.37	15.00	7.27	10.07	8.15	-10.84	-1.83	-0.71
NPISH	0.55	11.38	57.80	10.75	2.23	180.28	167.64	12.18
Government	13.17	3.43	4.94	25.59	9.61	153.17	104.41	15.07
Individual	13.20	3.43	4.92	25.60	5.19	163.38	111.91	18.79
Collective	13.16	3.43	4.95	25.59	11.06	149.81	101.94	13.84
Quarter on Quarter (QoQ)								
Quarter	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4
Households	-15.14	9.03	11.74	6.46	-16.61	-10.12	23.04	-42.05
NPISH	24.48	55.84	45.71	38.26	14.91	21.07	39.14	-42.05
Government	-3.42	-4.62	2.19	33.40	-15.71	120.32	-17.49	-24.90
Individual	-3.39	-4.62	2.15	33.44	-19.10	138.81	-17.81	-25.20
Collective	-3.43	-4.61	2.21	33.39	-14.60	114.55	-17.38	-24.80

Source: World Bank Data Base

In Q3 and Q4 2020, the real general government expenditure grew by 99.18% and 12.13% respectively, compared to 2.26% in 2019. On an annual basis, real growth for general government expenditure in 2020 stood at 61.58% compared to 8.78% in 2019. Quarter on quarter, growth was recorded at -18.02% and -25.39% in Q3 and Q4 respectively. In the nominal terms, government expenditure grew by 104.41% in Q3 and 15.07% in Q4 2020 resulting in an annual nominal growth rate 65.52% in 2020. Government expenditure however, grew more rapidly in 2020 than in 2019 by 53.35% points. In 2020, this component accounted for 9.40% of total real GDP expenditure at market price.

3. Evaluation of Economic Wellbeing of Nigerians in Pre and Post Covid-19 Era

Economic well-being matters a lot to policy makers and economists. Economic well-being is a vast topic, it cut across the measures of how the citizens of a country feel with the economic standard. In a more terms, economic well-being refer to a household's command over goods and services produced in the economy and in turn, its ability to maintain a minimum material standard of living it's often measured with income or consumption expenditure. In order to evaluate the economic well-being, we employed indicators such as poverty headcount, level of happiness ranking, hunger index and prosperity index. Outcome from our findings shows that in pre covid-19 era, poverty headcount for Nigeria was 31.54% in the year 2015; but it increased to 46.9% in 2016 and even reduced to 39.1% in 2017. In the preceeding year 2018, it reduced to 28% and increased to 40.1% in 2019. This shows that there is a great need for government intervention policies in order to lift the households from abject poverty. The rate of the poverty head count increased to 45.2% in covid-19 era due to economic hardship Nigerians experienced during covid-19 period. And in 2021 – post covid-19 era, the rate of poverty headcount for Nigeria was 60.34%. Measures such as reviving of other sectors of the economy with much interest on boosting the growth of small and medium enterprises so as to create more jobs and generate more income for household consumption.

Table 4: Economic Well-Being of Nigeria in Pre and Post Covid-19 Era

	PRE COVID-19 ERA					COVID-19 ERA	POST COVID-19 ERA
	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
POVERTY HEADCOUNT	31.54%	46.9%	39.1%	28%	40.1%	45.2%	60.34%
LEVEL OF HAPPINESS RANKING	116	115	85	91	95	40	42
HUNGER INDEX	32.80	25.50	25.50	31.10	27.9	29.2	58.3
PROSPERITY INDEX	41.47	41.22	42.14	42.73	42.35	42.92	20.1

Source: Knoema Atlas, Nigerian Ranking, Global Hunger Index and Legatum Index

Another measure of economic well-being was also utilized and our findings are as follows. In pre covid-19 era, Nigerians level of happiness was ranked 116 in 2015, 115 in 2016, 85 in 2017, 91 in 2018, and 95 in 2019. During the covid-19 period, the rank of level of happiness of Nigerians reduced to 40 and 42 in the post covid-19 era (see table 4). Furthermore, hunger index is a tool that is used to measure and track hunger globally as well as by region and by country. In the stance of Nigeria in pre covid-19 era, hunger index was 32.80 in 2015, it reduced to 25.00 in both 2016 and 2017. It went up to 31.10 and lowered to 27.9 in 2018 and 2019 respectively. Following the outbreak of covid-19 in Nigeria, hunger index increased to 29.2 in the year 2020 and increased further to 58.3 in post covid-19 era. The report of the prosperity index indicate that Nigeria's prosperity is revolving around 41 to 42 in the pre covid-19 era. In 2015, Nigeria's prosperity index was 41.47, 41.22 in 2016, 42.14 in 2017, 42.73 in 2018 and 42.35 in 2019. During covid-19 period, the prosperity index of Nigeria stood at 42.92 but diminished to 20.1 in post covid-19 era.

4. Government Efforts towards Improving Household Consumption And Economic Welfare Of Nigerians In Pre And Post Covid-19 Era

Federal government of Nigeria through the central bank has set out a number of measures to tackle the impact of covid-19 on household consumption and welfare of her citizenry. Some of the measures including establishment of a fund to support the country's economy (N50 billion; i.e. EUR121 million) targeted at households and small and medium enterprises (SMEs) on the monetary policy aspect. Furthermore, the interest rate has been cut, a moratorium has been announced on principal repayments for CBN intervention facilities and tax measures are being taken. On 16 March 2020, the Central bank of Nigeria announced new measures based on the N50 billion fund it released to stimulate the consumption expenditure and welfare of Nigerians. Measures such as: 1 year extension of a moratorium on principal repayments for CBN intervention facilities; the reduction of the interest rate on the intervention loans from 9 percent to 5 percent; strengthening of the loan to deposit ratio policy (i.e. stepped up enforcement of directive to extend more credit to private sector; creation of NGN50 billion target credit facility for affected households and small and medium enterprises; granting regulatory forbearance to banks to restructure terms of facilities in affected sectors; improving foreign exchange supply of to CBN by directing oil companies and oil servicing companies to FX to CBN rather than the Nigerian national petroleum corporation; approve additional NGN100 billion intervention fund in for of healthcare loans for pharmaceutical companies and healthcare practitioners intending to expand/build capacity; and identification of few key local pharmaceutical companies that will be granted funding facilities to support the procurement of raw materials and equipment required to boost local drug production. Furthermore CBN approved N1 trillion in loans to boost local manufacturing and production across critical sectors; adopted a unified exchange rate system for inter-bank and parallel market rates to ease pressure on FOREX earnings as well as oil prices continues to plummet; adopts the official N360 to a dollar for international money transfer operators rate to banks; it directed the financial institutions to engage international development partners and negotiate concessions to ease the pains of the borrowers on lending facilities of the borrowers and provision of credit assistance for the health industry to meet the potential increase in demand for health services and products by facilitating borrowing conditions for pharmaceutical companies, hospitals and practitioners.

Using Fiscal policy, the federal government of Nigeria reduced crude oil benchmark price from USD 57 to USD 30. Central Bank pledged to pump NGN 1.1 trillion (USD 3 billion) in to critical sectors of the economy;

commencement of a three month repayment moratorium for all TraderMoni, MarketMoni and FarmerMoni loans; and similar moratorium to all federal government funded loans issued by the bank of industry, bank of agriculture and the Nigerian export-import bank. Federal government revises planned spending in the 2020 budget with an increase of about N0.23trillion in expenditure and a 31% decrease in revenue. On April 1 2020, the Nigerian electricity regulatory commission (NERC) suspended the payment of the new electricity tariffs scheduled to commence on 2nd April 2020, citing poor electricity supply, wide metering gap and the impact of Covid-19 pandemic. The national assembly recently postponed the effective date of the new tariff to the first quarter of 2021. On October 11, NERC suspended the Multi Year Tariff Order (MYTO) 2020 for the electricity distribution licensees for 2 weeks. On 16 April 2020, Nigerian immigration service (NIS) announced the grant of payment waiver to visitors/migrants affected by the travel ban and closure of international airports. Affected persons are expected to reschedule their flight and travel within a week of the suspension of the restriction. The Lagos state government reverts annual land use charges to pre-2018 rate. And taxpayers in Nigeria need to consider the impact of coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic on their businesses and in particular the expected increase in debt default rate, cancellations of contracts or no-shows.

In the real sector, the federal government launched some programme to create jobs in the digital outsourcing. N90bn for the launch of a national programme to promote domestic use of CNG and support the creation of 1 million jobs. N23.4bn to support the creation of 1 million jobs through the conversion of 30 million homes from dirty fuels (kerosene, charcoal and diesel) to LPG and achieve emissions reconstruction in greenhouses gases while also applying LPG in other sectors such as agriculture, power generation, transport, industry and technology. N15bn to sustain 300,000 jobs in 100,000 MSME by guaranteeing off-take of identified priority products; N260bn to establish the SME Survival Fund to sustain at least 500,000m jobs in 50,000 SMEs for 3 months.

5. Summary of Findings, Policy Implications and Conclusion

This study centered on assessment of household consumption expenditure in pre and post covid-19 era in Nigeria. The sole aim is to ascertain how the household consumption expenditure was affected during and after covid-19 era in Nigeria. Covid-19 have great negative effects on Nigerians; the total lockdown imposed by the government in order to reduce the spread of the disease, crumbled economic activities, which affects the household consumption expenditure, level of income and investment. However, in order to examine if household consumption expenditure improved or not, we examined measures such as household consumption expenditure, purchasing power parity (PPP), foreign remittances, household disposable income, and household consumer confidence was assessed from 2015 to 2021 and the findings shows that covid-19 contributed to fall in Nigerian household consumption expenditure. Due to ban on business travels, the foreign remittances dropped drastically during covid-19 era because diaspora Nigerians doesn't incentives to send money home because they are also in economic crisis where they. Furthermore, we captured the growth in consumption in real and nominal terms, consumptions made by households, government, individual and non-profit institutions serving households (NPISH) and it was discovered that growth on consumption occurred in the aforesaid economic agents. In order to ascertain the well-being of the households, measures such as poverty headcounts, level of happiness, hunger index, and prosperity index was assessed. Findings shows that due to outbreak of covid-19 pandemic in Nigeria, the rate of poverty headcounts increased during and post covid-19 era; level of happiness diminished and rate of hunger increased (see table 4) when compared to previous years in pre covid-19 era. However, there was a slight decrease in Nigerian prosperity index in covid-19 era and post covid-19 era. In order to enhance household consumption, and make small and medium enterprises to thrive amidst covid-19 pandemic, Nigerian government employed various options such as fiscal and monetary options by enacting some programmes, injecting some stimulus funds like house hold survival funds and funds to encourage healthcare system yet, covid-19 pandemic still left negative scars on Nigerians. Based on the above findings, this study concludes that covid-19 pandemic have negative impact on household consumption expenditure. Hence we suggest that agricultural sector and food-chain supply should be enhanced by the federal government of Nigeria. Farmers should be empowered so as to embrace mechanized farming and boost the food production in

Nigeria. Furthermore, Nigerian government should diversify her economy to create more jobs and increase domestic manufacturing order than relying on imports.

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